

2 Links to websites

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Introduction

GLIS' main function is facilitating access to information about Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture (PGRFA). By design, GLIS stores a very limited amount of information on each PGRFA and rather helps users access information where it is created and maintained in other systems.

Each PGRFA registered in GLIS can have one or more links to such systems that are made available in the corresponding GLIS DOI detail page.

This document explains how those links are provided to GLIS, what is their function and what they can provide to users.

An example of links associated to a DOI in GLIS

Figure 1 below shows an example DOI with 2 links associated. The list of links is presented as table with the following columns:

- *Keywords* This column contains a comma-separated list of keywords taken from a controlled vocabulary identifying the kind of information the user would find if she clicked the corresponding link. For example, clicking the first link in the list will take to a web page where Passport data and Characterization details will be available for the PGRFA associated to DOI 10.18730/5BQ. The purpose of these keywords is to help the user quickly identify, among the available websites, those that are more likely to provide the information she is looking for;
- *URL* Contains the URL of the web page or, more in general, the URL of the web resource associated to the PGRFA being displayed. We recommend stakeholders to provide the URL of the actual page related to the specific PGRFA, and not the URL of the home page of their website, to facilitate the user.

Should the number of links in the page exceed 5, a paging and filtering function will be presented allowing the user to quickly show only the links associated to a specific keyword.

Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations

English

Home Statistics DOI module Partners Login

PGRFA doi:10.18730/5BQ

Citation: <https://doi.org/10.18730/5BQ>

Main descriptors Acquisition Collection DOI info

Organization/individual conserving the PGRFA	Centro Internacional de la Papa Av. La Molina Nº 1895 - La Molina Lima Peru WIEWS code: PER001 [Details] Easy-SMTA PID: 00AD19	Biological status	Traditional cultivar/landrace
Local identifier	CIP 201222	Names	
Date	1993	Other identifiers	
Creation method	Acquisition	MLS status	Included
Taxon	Ullucus tuberosus Caldas subsp. tuberosus	Historical	No
Common name	Andean Root and Tubers		

Links to associated information (1-3 of 3)

Keywords	URL
Passport data, Characterization	http://genebank.cipotato.org/gringlobal/accessiondetail.aspx?id=20726
Passport data	https://www.genesys-pgr.org/10.18730/5BQ
Passport data	http://www.fao.org/wiews/data/ex-situ-sdg-251/search/en/?doi=10.18730/5BQ#details

Publications and datasets citing this PGRFA (1-1 of 1)

Type	Title	Published	Journal	Authors	Publisher
Paper	Ullucus tuberosus Caldas: colección de germoplasma de ullucu conservada en el Centro Internacional de la Papa (CIP)	2017-05	CGSpace	Manrique, I., Arbizu, C., Vivanco, F., Gonzáles, R., Ramírez, C.A., Chávez, O., Tay, D., Ellis, D.	CGIAR

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Figure 1: Example PGRFA page with the list of associated links at the bottom

How links are provided to GLIS

Links can be provided to GLIS as follows:

- by entering them in the web form when registering a new PGRFA or updating one that is already registered, see Figure 2 below showing the page as available to the owner of the DOI that offers a button to add a new link and a way to delete existing links,
- by listing them in the Excel template used for batch registration. Figure 3 shows the area of the Excel template with columns L and M (descriptor R01) where the URL and the keyword code can be entered for each PGRFA being registered,
- in the XML protocol, by providing the URL and associated keywords in the <targets> element of the message as shown in Figure 4 below.

Depending on the specific case, stakeholders can choose any of the three options to obtain the same result.

Figure 2: Button "+ Add new link" and trash can icon to add and delete links associated to the PGRFA

K	L	M	
Common name			
M05	R01	R01	
Common name	Links to associated information	Link keyword codes	DOI
	http://my.ita.org/accession2/accession/TVu-17476	1	
	http://my.ita.org/accession2/accession/TVu-17477	1	
	http://my.ita.org/accession2/accession/TVu-17478	1	
	http://my.ita.org/accession2/accession/TVu-17479	1	
	http://my.ita.org/accession2/accession/TVu-17480	1	

Figure 3: Fragment of the Excel registration template showing columns L and M

```

...
<targets>
<target>
<value>http://www.nordgen.org/sgsv/index.php?unit_id=239741</value>
<kws>
<kw>5</kw>
</kws>
</target>
</targets>
...

```

Figure 4: Fragment of the XML message showing the new link being provided

External systems registering themselves as links in GLIS

Thanks to the collaboration with the Global Crop Diversity Trust, Genesys (<https://www.genesys-pgr.org>) is allowed to register its own page on the PGRFA as one of the links associated to a GLIS DOI. In Figure 2 above, the link has been added directly by Genesys through this integration. More details on the integration with Genesys are available in the GLIS Technical Note 7, Genesys Integration.

A similar function has been implemented in EURISCO¹, an initiative gathering about 400 institutes in Europe.

¹ See <https://eurisco.ipk-gatersleben.de>

I am not fully clear on what needs to be done, please help!

Should you require further clarifications, please do not hesitate to send an email to PGRFA-Treaty@fao.org and we will be delighted to assist!